

Correlation analysis and effect of excess free energy of solvents for the kinetics of oxidation of benzhydrol by tetrabutylammoniumbromochromate

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Abstract : The oxidation of benzhydrol (BH) by tetrabutylammoniumbromochromate (TBABC) was studied in the presence of perchloric acid, in water/organic solvent mixtures of varying excess molar free energy function. The reaction is first order with respect to both TBABC and acid. The reaction rates were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters computed. A correlation of data with the Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic parameters (α , β , π^*) suggests that the specific solute-solvent interactions play a major role in governing the reactivity. The reaction does not induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. The product of oxidation is benzophenone. Based on the kinetic results and product analysis, a suitable mechanism has been proposed for the reaction of TBABC with benzhydrol.

Keywords : Tetrabutylammoniumbromochromate, benzhydrol, oxidation, kinetics.

Introduction

The kinetics of oxidation of organic compounds in non-aqueous and aquo-organic solvent mixtures has revealed the important role of non-specific and specific solvent effects on reactivity¹⁻⁵. It has been shown that the reactivity is influenced by the preferential solvation of the reactants and/or transition state through non-specific and specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions. Further, it has been established that the technique of correlation analysis may well be used to separate and quantify such solvent-solvent-solute interactions on reactivity.

Blandamer and Burgess⁶ classified aqueous mixtures based on their thermodynamic properties, particularly their molar excess functions, X^E . Solvent mixtures are very useful for studying solvent effects upon reactions, since the properties of various mixed solvents can be adjusted continuously by changing

the composition of the mixture. Thus, in this article, the solvent mixtures such as water/1,4-dioxane (apolar, aprotic, hydrogen bond acceptor solvent), water/DMF (polar, aprotic, hydrogen bond acceptor solvent), water/acetonitrile, water/acetone (both dipolar aprotic non-hydrogen bond donor solvent), and water/*t*-BuOH (protic, hydrogen bond donor solvent) have been chosen. Solvent variations may affect the kinetics and the energy of the electron transfer processes in a complex manner, particularly in mixed solvent media as the physico-chemical properties of mixed solvent media are often quite different from those of the pure solvents or of their ideal mixtures⁷.

A variety of compounds containing chromium(VI) have proved to be versatile reagents capable of oxidizing almost every oxidizing functional group⁸. A number of new chromium containing compounds like tripropylammoniumfluorochromate⁹, tetraethylammo-

niurchlorochromate¹⁰ and tetraheptylammonium-bromochromate¹¹ have been used to study the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of various organic compounds. Recently tetrabutylammoniumbromochromate (TBABC) has been reported as a new and stronger oxidizing agent¹².

Benzhydrols yield benzophenones upon oxidation, which are useful synthones for fullerenes, bioactive oxygen heterocyclics, dyes, and medicines. A literature search showed that there seems to various oxidizing agents, such as chloramine-B¹³, *N*-bromosuccinimide¹⁴, Tl(III)¹⁵, *N*-bromophthalimide¹⁶ and permanganate¹⁷ have been used to study the oxidation of benzhydrol.

As a part of our continuing investigations of the oxidation of organic substrates by Cr(VI)¹⁸⁻²⁰, we report the kinetic features of the oxidation of benzhydrol by TBABC in the solvent mixtures such as water/DMF, water/1,4-dioxane, water/acetone, water/*t*-BuOH and water/acetonitrile of varying mole fractions. The objective of the present work includes a systematic study of the solvent effects with the view of understanding of the mechanism of benzhydrols.

Experimental

Materials :

Tetrabutylammonium bromide and chromium trioxide were obtained from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). Benzhydrol is obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Acetic acid was purified by standard method and the fraction distilling at 118°C was collected. TBABC was prepared by reported method¹² and its purity is checked by an iodometric method. Deuterated (α -C-D) benzhydrol was prepared by the method of Shanker and Suresh²¹. α -D benzhydrols were prepared by refluxing benzhydrol (α -C-H) in D₂O for 2-3 h, removing the solvent under pump, and repeating the process three times to ensure complete exchange of protons. PMR analysis was conducted to confirm the deuterated (α -C-D) benzhydrols.

Kinetic measurements :

The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or more) of

benzhydrol over TBABC. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (± 0.01 K), by monitoring the decrease in [TBABC] spectrophotometrically at 364 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometer, Shimadzu UV-1800 model. The pseudo-first order rate constant k_1 , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990$ to 0.999) plots of \log [TBABC] against time for up to 80% reaction. The second order rate constant k_2 , was obtained from the relation $k_2 = k_1 / [\text{Substrate}]$.

Data analysis :

Correlation analysis was carried out using Microcal origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using the correlation coefficient (r in the case of simple linear regression and R in the case of multiple linear regressions) and standard deviation (SD).

Results and discussion

The oxidation of benzhydrol (BH) by tetrabutylammoniumbromochromate (TBABC) was studied in the presence of perchloric acid, in water/organic solvent mixtures of varying excess molar free energy function under pseudo-first order conditions. Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. The oxidation of benzhydrol resulted in the formation of the corresponding benzophenone. The DNP of benzophenone was determined by a reported method¹⁸. The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined¹⁸ by performing the experiment under the conditions of TBABC > BH.

Order of the reaction :

The concentration of TBABC was varied in the range of 0.5×10^{-3} to 2.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ at constant [BH], [H⁺] at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The near constancy in the value of k_1 irrespective of the concentration confirms the first order dependence on TBABC (Table 1). The rate of oxidation increased progressively on increasing the concentration of benzhydrol. The plot of $\log k_1$ versus \log [BH] gave a slope nearly unity for BH. Under pseudo-first order conditions, the plot of k_1 versus [BH] is linear passing through origin. These results confirm the first order nature of the reaction

Table 1. Effect of variation of [BH], [TBABC] and [H⁺] on the rate of reaction in water/DMF, water/1,4-dioxane, water/acetone, water/*t*-BuOH and water/acetonitrile mixtures of 0.5 mole fractions at 303 K^a

(mol dm ⁻³)			10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)				
10 ³ [TBABC]	10 ² [S]	10 [H ⁺]	Water/DMF	Water/1,4-Dioxane	Water/Acetone	Water/ <i>t</i> -BuOH	Water/MeCN
0.5	2.2	0.28	1.16	9.60	9.38	9.44	9.20
1.0	2.2	0.28	1.12	9.64	9.34	9.50	9.18
1.5	2.2	0.28	1.08	9.58	9.28	9.56	9.22
2.0	2.2	0.28	1.10	9.58	9.30	9.48	9.16
2.5	2.2	0.28	1.14	9.68	9.32	9.54	9.14
1.0	1.2	0.28	0.60	5.20	5.04	5.14	4.98
1.0	1.7	0.28	0.80	7.34	7.20	7.26	7.10
1.0	2.7	0.28	1.40	11.76	11.34	11.64	11.30
1.0	3.2	0.28	1.60	13.96	13.60	13.86	13.40
1.0	2.2	0.12	0.48	4.08	3.98	4.00	3.90
1.0	2.2	0.20	0.80	6.80	6.62	6.76	6.56
1.0	2.2	0.36	1.46	12.40	12.00	12.18	11.76
1.0	2.2	0.44	1.78	15.20	14.68	14.88	14.40
1.0	2.2	0.28	0.92 ^b	8.00 ^b	7.78 ^b	7.88 ^b	7.62 ^b

^aAs determined by spectrophotometrically following the disappearance of Cr^{VI} at 368 nm; estimated from pseudo-first order plots over 80% reaction.

^bIn the presence of 0.003 mol dm⁻³ Mn^{II}.

with respect to [BH].

The oxidation process is catalyzed in the presence of perchloric acid, and the reaction proceeds at a comfortable rate (Table 1). The oxidation is first order in perchloric acid. The plot of log *k*_{obs} versus log [H⁺] is a straight line with unit slope.

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile and effect of added MnSO₄ concentration :

No “milky appearance” was observed upon addition of stabilizer-free acrylonitrile (washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and distilled in water) to the reaction mixture in nitrogen atmosphere, therefore, the presence of free radical in the reaction is ruled out. Addition of Mn^{II}, in the form of MnSO₄ (0.003 M) retards the rate of the oxidation process indicating two electron oxidation (Table 1). This indicates the involvement of Cr^{IV} intermediate in the oxidation of aldehydes by Cr^{VI} reagent²².

Kinetic isotope effect :

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α-C-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of α-deuteriobenzhydrol was studied. Results

showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (*k*_H/*k*_D = 5.54 at 303 K).

Thermodynamic parameters :

The reactions were studied at four different temperatures (Table 2) to evaluate various thermodynamic parameters. The Arrhenius equation was found to be followed for benzhydrol studied. The various thermodynamic parameters as evaluated on the basis of these Arrhenius plots are recorded in Table 3.

Table 2. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidation of benzhydrol in water/DMF, water/1,4-dioxane, water/acetone, water/*t*-BuOH and water/acetonitrile mixtures of 0.5 mole fractions

Substrate	10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)			
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
H ₂ O/DMF	0.77	1.12	1.63	2.40
H ₂ O/1,4-Dioxane	7.26	9.64	12.80	17.12
H ₂ O/Acetone	6.91	9.34	12.58	16.98
H ₂ O/ <i>t</i> -BuOH	7.08	9.50	12.72	17.07
H ₂ O/MeCN	6.73	9.18	12.41	16.90

10² [S] = 2.2 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [TBABC] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³; 10 [H⁺] = 2.8 mol dm⁻³.

Table 3. Second order rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of benzhydrol in water/DMF, water/1,4-dioxane, water/acetone, water/*t*-BuOH and water/acetonitrile mixtures of 0.5 mole fractions

Solvent	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹) (at 303 K)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K				
H ₂ O/DMF	0.35	0.51	0.74	1.09	58.7	56.3±0.2	103.2±0.6	87.5±0.4
H ₂ O/1,4-Dioxane	3.30	4.38	5.82	7.78	44.4	41.9±0.7	132.7±2.1	82.1±1.3
H ₂ O/Acetone	3.14	4.24	5.72	7.72	47.3	44.0±0.5	125.8±1.5	82.2±1.0
H ₂ O/ <i>t</i> -BuOH	3.22	4.32	5.78	7.76	45.6	43.0±0.2	129.2±0.6	82.2±0.4
H ₂ O/MeCN	3.06	4.17	5.64	7.68	47.7	45.2±0.4	122.5±1.2	82.3±0.8

$10^2 [S] = 2.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [\text{TBABC}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10 [\text{H}^+] = 2.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Isokinetic temperature :

The reaction is neither isoenthalpic nor isoentropic but complies with the compensation law also known as the isokinetic relationship. The isokinetic temperature is the temperature at which all the compounds of the series react equally fast. The operation of the isokinetic relationship is tested by plotting the logarithms of rate constants at two different temperatures ($T_2 > T_1$) against each other according to eq. (1).

$$\log k \text{ (at } T_2) = a + b \log k \text{ (at } T_1) \quad (1)$$

The linear relationship in Exner plots²⁴ at $2 + \log k_2$ (at higher temperature) and $2 + \log k_2$ (at lower temperature) observed in the present study imply the validity of the isokinetic relationship. Isokinetic temperature obtained in different solvent mixtures are given in Table 4. The linear isokinetic correlation

Table 4. Isokinetic temperature for the oxidation of benzhydrol by TBABC in water/DMF, water/1,4-dioxane, water/acetone, water/*t*-BuOH and water/acetonitrile of 0.5 mole fractions

Temperature (K)	Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	Slope (<i>b</i>)	Isokinetic temperature (β), K
303 and 298	0.994	0.964	550
308 and 298	0.982	0.928	543
313 and 298	0.998	0.890	528
308 and 303	0.990	0.963	539
313 and 303	0.986	0.921	508
313 and 308	0.996	0.960	512

$10^2 [S] = 2.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [\text{TBABC}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10 [\text{H}^+] = 2.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

implies that benzhydrol in different solvent mixtures are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in the rate are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of activation²³.

Solvent-reactivity correlation :

The oxidation of benzhydrol by TBABC has been studied in water/DMF, water/1,4-dioxane, water/acetone, water/*t*-BuOH and water/acetonitrile of varying mole fractions, with a view to understand the effect of preferential solvation on the oxidation of the reaction. The results in Table 5 indicate that the rate constants (k_{obs}) are remarkably sensitive to the nature and the composition of the mixed solvent.

The binary aqueous mixtures chosen for the present study represent various classes of solvent mixtures according to Blandamar and Burgess⁶. Aqueous mixtures have been classified based on their thermodynamic properties, particularly their molar excess functions, X^E . Water/1,4-dioxane, water/acetone and water/*t*-BuOH mixtures are examples of the typical aqueous (TA) class, for which the excess Gibbs function, G^E , is positive. Water/MeCN is classified as a typical non-aqueous positive (TNAP) mixture (G^E is positive). Water/DMF falls into the typical non-aqueous negative (TNAN) category, for which G^E is negative. The properties of TA mixtures are particularly sensitive to the mole fraction of the non-aqueous co-solvent, x_2 . At low mole fractions, TA solvents exerts a water structure-forming action, the solvent co-spheres around each solute molecule overlap and mutually enhance water-water interactions. As more co-solvent is added, the mole fraction exceeds a criti-

Table 5. Effect of added organic co-solvents on the rate constant on the oxidation of benzhydrol by TBABC at 303 K

Mole fraction of organic co-solvent	$10^4 k_1$ (s^{-1})				
	DMF	1,4-Dioxane	Acetone	<i>t</i> -BuOH	MeCN
0.1	1.78	8.72	8.56	8.64	8.28
0.2	1.60	8.96	8.76	8.90	8.42
0.3	1.42	9.18	8.94	9.02	8.70
0.4	1.24	9.36	9.12	9.20	8.92
0.5	1.12	9.64	9.36	9.50	9.18
0.6	0.96	9.88	9.54	9.66	9.42
0.7	0.74	10.02	9.78	9.84	9.68
0.8	0.66	10.24	9.88	10.14	9.78

$10^2 [S] = 2.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [\text{TBABC}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10 [\text{H}^+] = 2.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

cal mole fraction, x_2^* , where there is insufficient water to maintain a three-dimensional hydrogen-bonded network of water molecules. In the TNAP mixtures, the co-solvent exerts a depolymerising effect on water and in this sense is a structure breaker. In TNAN mixtures, inter component association occurs which leads to a breakdown of the water-water interactions. Further, an extra-thermodynamic analysis indicates that, at least qualitatively, if G^E is positive, the solute should be more soluble in the mixture than predicted from its solubility in the individual pure solvents⁶. Various treatments for the above solvent-solute interactions based on Linear Solvation Energy Relationships (LSER) have been developed²⁴.

The Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic method :

This kind of dual dependency of the reactivity on the solvent composition is illustrated by the Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic comparison method²⁵. This method may be used to unravel, quantify, correlate and rationalize multiple interacting solvent effects on reactivity. Thus, the rate data were correlated with solvatochromic parameters in the form of the following linear solvation energy relationship (LSER) :

$$\log k = A_0 + s\pi^* + a\alpha + b\beta \quad (2)$$

where π^* is an index of the solvent dipolarity/polarizability, which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent hydrogen bond donor (HBD) acidity, which describes the ability of the

solvent to donate a proton, β is the solvent hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA) basicity, which provides a measure of the ability of the solvent to accept a proton (donate an electron pair), in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond, and A_0 is the regression value of the solute property in the reference solvent cyclohexane. The regression coefficients, s , a and b , measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ to the indicated solvent parameter. These solvatochromic parameters for the aqueous organic mixtures used in the present study were obtained from the literature²⁶. The rate of oxidation in the solvent mixture studied show good correlations with solvent via the above LSER. The correlation results obtained are given below.

In water/DMF mixtures :

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -3.562 \pm 1.78 - (0.622 \pm 0.42)\pi^* + (0.968 \pm 0.38)\alpha - (3.124 \pm 1.66)\beta$$

($N = 8$; $R = 0.991$; $R^2 = 0.982$; $Sd = 0.04$;
 $P_\alpha = 21\%$; $P_\beta = 67\%$; $P_{\pi^*} = 12\%$)

In water/1,4-dioxane mixtures :

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -0.942 \pm 0.68 - (1.480 \pm 0.68)\pi^* + (0.142 \pm 0.54)\alpha - (1.962 \pm 0.78)\beta$$

($N = 8$; $R = 0.986$; $R^2 = 0.972$; $Sd = 0.06$;
 $P_\alpha = 8\%$; $P_\beta = 55\%$; $P_{\pi^*} = 37\%$)

In water/acetone mixtures :

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -2.182 \pm 0.48 - (0.864 \pm 0.18)\pi^* + (0.011 \pm 0.01)\alpha - (0.938 \pm 0.24)\beta$$

($N = 8$; $R = 0.968$; $R^2 = 0.937$; $Sd = 0.03$;

$$P_{\alpha} = 0\%; P_{\beta} = 57\%; P_{\pi^*} = 43\%$$

In water/*t*-BuOH mixtures :

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -3.482 \pm 0.02 - (0.133 \pm 0.06)\pi^* - (0.021 \pm 0.04)\alpha - (0.108 \pm 0.02)\beta$$

$$(N = 8; R = 0.995; R^2 = 0.990; Sd = 0.05;$$

$$P_{\alpha} = 11\%; P_{\beta} = 43\%; P_{\pi^*} = 46\%)$$

In water/MeCN mixtures :

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -2.886 \pm 0.18 - (0.042 \pm 0.14)\pi^* - (0.268 \pm 0.16)\alpha - (0.924 \pm 0.12)\beta$$

$$(N = 8; R = 0.978; R^2 = 0.956; Sd = 0.01;$$

$$P_{\alpha} = 19\%; P_{\beta} = 77\%; P_{\pi^*} = 4\%)$$

Such good correlations, with an explained variance of 94–99% in the aqua-organic solvent mixtures, indicate the existence of non-specific and specific solvent-solute interactions. From the values of the regression coefficients, the contribution of each parameter (P_x), on a percentage basis, to the reactivity were calculated²⁷. The following conclusions were drawn from the systematic correlation studies :

(i) The contribution of the solvent HBA term is dominant in all the mixtures, except *t*-BuOH, as indicated by the percentage contributions of this term, P_{β} compared to P_{α} and P_{π^*} . This may be because all the co-solvents are typical HBA solvents. Hence, increasing the mole fraction of these solvents in the mixture increases the solute-solvent interactions through the HBA property.

(ii) The sign of the coefficient of the α term is positive in the water/DMF, water/1,4-dioxane and water/acetone mixtures, suggesting that the transition state-solvent interactions, through specific HBD property, dominate over the reactant-solvent interactions.

(iii) In all the investigated solvent mixtures, except MeCN, the contribution of both specific and non-specific solute-solvent interactions play dominant roles, as indicated by the percentage contributions of the α , β and π^* terms. In case of MeCN, the contribution of the specific property is dominant.

(iv) The sign of the coefficient of the β and π^* terms in all the investigated mixtures is negative,

indicating the reactants are solvated to a larger extent than the transition state through the HBA and dipolarity/polarizability properties.

(v) In water/*t*-BuOH and water/MeCN mixtures, the sign of the coefficient of the α term is negative, indicating the reactants are solvated through HBD property to a larger extent than the transition state.

Therefore, it is concluded that both specific (microscopic) and non-specific (macroscopic) solute-solvent interactions play a dominant role in governing the reactivity of the substrate under investigation. Furthermore, a dynamic exchange of solvent molecules between the solvation shell of the transition state and the bulk exists⁷.

Mechanism of oxidation :

From the product analysis, DNP was confirmed. Hence, it shows that under the experimental conditions employed in the present study, benzhydrol is oxidized to benzophenone. Absence of any effect of added acrylonitrile on the reaction discounts the possibility of a one-electron oxidation, leading to the formation of free radicals. However, the addition of Mn^{II} ($0.003 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), in the form of MnSO_4 retards the rate of oxidation (Table 1). This indicates the involvement of Cr^{IV} intermediate in the oxidation of benzhydrol by Cr^{VI} reagent. Catalysis by perchloric acid suggests protonation of TBABC species. The protonated TBABC is difficult to visualize but participation of protonated chromium(VI) oxidation is well known²⁸. Based on the above kinetic observations the following mechanism is proposed for the reaction.

The presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect in the oxidation of α -deuteriobenzhydrol confirms the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. Therefore, a hydride-ion transfer in the rate determining step is suggested (Scheme 1). As the concentration of the organic component in the solvent mixture increases, the greater is the number of organic solvent molecules introduced into the solvation shell. As the mole fraction of the organic com-

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Scheme 1. Mechanism of oxidation of benzhydrol by TBABC.

ponent in the solvent mixture increases, the greater is the stabilization of the transition state through HBD/HBA solute-solvent interactions.

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